

Performance Analysis of Solar Dryer as Renewable Energy Source

¹Prof. D. R. Thawkar, ²Prof. V. H. Bankar, ³Prof. Kalyani K. Sengar, ⁴Prof. Aman G. Dhanvijay

Abstract— The scenario in energy consumption in India is same than that of other part of continent. It is a matter of concern that the capita energy consumption data is very low in spite of high rate of development taking place. India is one of the largest consumers of fossil fuel such as crude oil, coal etc. This rapid increase in use of Nonrenewable energies such as natural gas, fossil fuel, oil, coal has created intense problems of demand & supply. In most of the developing countries, where electricity grid connection is unavailable or either unreliable, renewable energies such as solar energy are used. The scenario of food crises is also not different from that of energy. Scarcity of food due to large amount of wastage and improper handling has let to preservation of food. This paper emphasizes on the preservation of food with utilization of renewable energy.

Keywords— Solar drying, solar collector, Angle of Tilt and Collector efficiency

I. INTRODUCTION

India was the eleventh largest economy in the world, and had been ranked fourth in terms of purchasing power as per the past reports. In the year 2011, India's installed power capacity was about 210645 MW with renewable energy contributing almost 26,900 MW or 12.4%. Of this, 69% is generation from wind and 4.5% from solar. India has had a negative Energy Balance for past few decades, which have ultimately resulted purchase of energy from other countries to fulfill the demands of the entire country. Energy is one of the major parameter taken into consideration for estimating the growth and progress of the country, or it could be said that the standard of living depends directly upon the per capita energy consumption

Manuscript Received June 30, 2023; Revised 15 September, 2023 and Published on September 30, 2023

Prof. Prof. D. R. Thawkar, Department of Mechanical Engineering, Vidarbha Institute of Technology, Nagpur, Maharashtra, India Maharashtra, India. Mail Id: idthawkar2017@gmail.com

Prof. V. H. Bankar, Department of Mechanical Engineering, Vidarbha Institute of Technology, Nagpur, Maharashtra, India Maharashtra, India. Mail Id: vhbankar@gmail.com

Prof. Kalyani K. Sengar, Department of Mechanical Engineering, Suryodaya College Of Engineering And Technology Nagpur, Maharashtra, India. Mail Id: kalyanisingh1804@gmail.com

Prof. Aman G. Dhanvijay, Department of Mechanical Engineering, Vidarbha Institute of Technology, Nagpur, Maharashtra, India Maharashtra, India. Mail Id: amandhanvijay358@gmail.com

The per capita consumption in India is accounted to be 400 KWH per annum. Most of the power plants in India use the conventional energy sources, coal and oils which has a great impact in addition of greenhouse gases in atmosphere. India was the first country to set up a ministry of non-conventional energy resources in 1980s.

A torque wrench is a tool used to precisely apply a specific Among the various renewable energy resources used, solar energy potential is the highest in India than of other countries. The power from the sun in form of solar radiation intercepted by the earth is approximate ly 1.8 x 10¹¹ MW. In most parts of India, clear sunny weather is experienced 200 to 250 days a year. The annual radiation varies from 1600 to 21500 kWh/m², which is almost comparable with radiation received in the tropical and sub-tropical regions. The equivalent energy potential is about 6,000 million GWh of energy per year is observed.

Solar radiations in the form of thermal energy is used for preservation of fruits, vegetables and grains which is essential for increasing the life, and process the food items in clean, hygienic and sanitary environmental conditions. Several other technologies are employed to preserve the food such as freezing, canning, etc. which could not be used for all type of products. Solar drying is a simple process in which the moisture content of the product is removed to preserve the food. Thus removal of moisture prevents the reproduction and growth of microorganism ms like yeasts, moulds and bacteria which causes deterioration and decay of the product.

Drying involves removal of moisture from the agricultural commodity so it can last longer. Solar drying is a method of removal of moisture due to simultaneous heat and mass transfer by utilization of incident solar radiation. Solar dryer's uses solar energy as an energy source and control the drying process and protect agricultural produce from damage by dust, insect pests and rain. With comparison to natural "sun drying", solar dryers get higher temperatures, lower product moisture content, lower relative humidity, and reduced spoilage during the drying process. In addition, it takes less time, up less space and relatively inexpensive compared to artificial mechanical drying method. Thus, this type of solar drying is a better alternative solution to all the drawbacks of natural drying and artificial mechanical drying.

II. LITERATURE SURVEY

F. K. Forson et al [1] fabricated a mixed-mode natural convection solar crop dryer. Three main components of the dryer were: an air-heater primary collector, by which the drying air is heated as it flows over and under an absorber plate

that is heated in turn by direct absorption of incident radiation; a drying chamber is there in which the crop to be dried is kept; and a chimney, through which the moist air flows and escapes into the surrounding. Solar energy is incident on the planes of the primary collector and the drying chamber. The primary collector is a single pass air-heater with double duct (SPDDSAH) and a nonporous absorber plate suspended between the top glass cover and the base plate providing two channels (upper and lower channels) through which air flows in the same direction on Both sides of the absorber plate thus providing twice as much roof of the drying chamber (i.e. secondary collector) and sidewalls are transparent. Doors are provided for access to the chamber for loading, unloading, and stirring of the crop. The chimney runs along the entire breadth of the drying chamber to aid the natural circulation of air inside the whole box. An exit air vent runs across the width of the drying chamber.

Padmanabhan S. Chandrasekaran. M. And Srinivasa Raman. V V. Shanmugam et al [2] fabricated a solar dryer consisting of a flat plate collector, drying chamber, desiccant bed, blower and circulation fan as shown in Fig.

1. An 18 gauge copper sheet painted matte black is used as an absorber plate to absorb incident solar radiation. The dimension of flat plate collector is about 1.2×2.4 m² and is kept facing south tilted at an angle of 30°. A 6-mm plain window glass is used as transparent cover to avoid heat losses at the top. The collector air channel depth is

20 mm and the space between the absorber to the transparent glass cover is 25 mm. The collector frame is made of locally available thick wood and at the bottom 19 mm plywood is provided to support the absorber plate. A 50 mm thick fine wood saving is used as insulation on the sides and at the bottom of the absorber plate to prevent heat losses. The drying chamber of dimensions $1.2 \times 1.2 \times 1.0$ m³ is fabricated from 19 mm thick insulated plywood. Double glazing is provided at the top of the drying chamber with an air gap of 50 mm and inclined at 30° as like flat plate collector in order to increase the total energy collected and to reduce the net thermal loss from the desiccant bed. A perforated sheet is provided to hold 75 kg of solid desiccants below the double glazing. The space between the bottom glass cover and the desiccant bed is 50 mm. The depth of the desiccant bed is

75 mm. A provision is made to include 25 mm thick insulated plywood just above and below the desiccant bed. During the daytime operation, the plywood is placed at the bottom of the desiccant bed, so that the air coming out from the drying chamber will not interact with the desiccant unit and escapes through the vent provided. During off-sunshine Hours, the plywood sheet is placed above the desiccant bed to avoid heat losses at the top. The useful temperature difference in the desiccant bed remains always higher while using insulation cover just below the glazing than using insulation at the top of the glass cover. The drying trays are made using wire mesh fixed on wooden frame with dimensions 1.0×1.0 m² to hold the drying

product. The trays are kept on the wooden frame fixed to the inner side walls of the drying chamber and can be easily removed to load or unload the drying product. A small opening is provided on the eastern side of the drying chamber to weigh the drying products. A

1.47 kW centrifugal blower rotating at 2800 rpm is used

to circulate the hot air to the drying chamber through the provided to regulate the air flow. A small capacity two-way fan is used to draw the ambient air through the desiccant bed for regeneration during sunshine hours and to circulate the air inside the drying chamber in the off-sunshine hours. The desiccant used in this study is a mixture of 60% bentonite, 10% calcium chloride, 20% vermiculite and 10% cement by weight, as specified by Thoruwaeta. This desiccant is processed at 50 °C for 24 h and dried at 200 °C for 24 h in a vacuum furnace. Copper constantan thermocouples are used to measure the temperature at various locations of the system. A calibrated solar meter is used to measure the solar radiation incident on the surfaces. A hygrometer is used to measure the relative humidity of the air. The mass flow rate of air is measured using calibrated Pitot tube. The wind speed is measured using wind anemometer. An electronic balance of 0.001 g accuracy is used to measure the weight of the drying products.

III. EXPERIMENTAL SETUP

A. Method

The most commonly seen design types are of cabinet form, having two main parts i.e. the solar collector (air heater), and drying chamber. Solar collector consists of assembly of absorber plate (flat plate collector) and glass cover. They are separated by some distance to provide passage for air movement. The absorber plate is painted with black colour to absorb maximum radiation incident on it. Solar radiation enters through the transparent glass cover and absorbed by the absorber plate, the glass cover avoids reflection of solar radiation back to atmosphere (green house effect). The ambient air at atmospheric temperature enters at inlet of solar collector and passes over heated flat plate collector and flows over it in upward direction due to decrease in density. So fresh air is entered at inlet of collector and due to density difference between air at inlet and outlet of collector the continuous flow of air is maintained (thermo siphon effect). The warm air leaving at outlet of collector enters in drying chamber. Drying chamber contains number of mesh type drying trays separated by adequate distance so air movement is maintained in the drying chamber. Food is placed on the trays, so hot air flowing in the chamber evaporates the moisture present in the food and get saturated and carry with air stream outside the chamber through opening provided at the top of the chamber. The hot air acts as the drying medium, it extracts and conveys the moisture from the produce (or food) to the atmosphere under free (natural) convection, thus the system is a passive solar system and no external power source is required for its operation.

B. Design consideration

1. Ambient condition (temperature, relative humidity and

velocity of air): the minimum and maximum temperature allowable for selected agro commodity is taken into consideration. the minimum temperature is taken as ambient temperature (30 °C) and maximum allowable temperature is 60 °C. The design is made for maximum temperature of 60°C (outlet temperature of collector).

2. Air gap: For passive solar dryer it is suggested that an air vent (inlet) of 5 cm should be created

3. Glass: It suggested that the glass covering should be 4- 5 mm thickness. In this work, 4mm thick transparent glass was used.

4 Absorber plate: It is suggested that the metal sheet thickness should be of 0.8 – 1.0 mm thickness in this work flat plate absorber plate of mild steel of 1.0mm thickness was used.

5. Drying chamber: In this setup work the drying chamber was made up of wood. It protects the food to be placed on the trays from direct sunlight since this is undesirable and tends to bleach colour, removes flavor and causes the food to dry unevenly

6. Angle of tilt of solar collector: The angle of tilt of solar collector is determined with the help of latitude of the collector location. (Angle of tilt = lat (φ) +100)

7. Dryer trays: Wire mesh type pattern is selected as screen for dryer trays for proper air circulation within the drying chamber. Wood sticks are used as frame. The dimension of the drying chamber was

1. Angle of Tilt (β) of Solar Collector

It states that the angle of tilt (β) of the solar collector should be $\beta = 100 + \text{lat } \phi$

Where lat φ is the latitude of the collector location, the latitude of Chandwad(NASHIK) where the dryer was designed and tested is at latitude 20.310N.

Therefore, the angle of tilt for the collector is $\beta = 100 + 20.310 = 30.310$

Collector dimension: The measurement of air speed is done with the help of anemometer. at the time of trial it varies from 0.2 to 0.4 m/s. for calculation it is taken as $V_a = 0.2 \text{ m/s}$

The collector opening at inlet (i.e. height and width) was taken as height =4.5 cm and width =37 cm.

Therefore, volumetric air flow rate of air $V_a = V_a$

Density of air ρ_a is taken as 1.28kg/ m³

$M_a = 0.0333 \times 1.28$

$= 0.0042624 \text{ Kg/s}$

The useful heat gain by a collector is determined as Q_C

$= M_a \times C_p \times (T_o - T_i)$

$= 0.00426 \times 1.005 \times (60 - 30)$

$= 0.1285 \text{ KJ/S}$

The area of collector can be found as $Q_C = I \times A_c \times \tau \times \alpha$

Where, I=Intensity of solar radiation (it is measured with the help of solar meter) =0.7 kW/ m²

A_c = area of collector surface

τ = transitivity of glass and = 0.8

α = absorptive of absorber plate = 0.9 Therefore, $A_c = 0.25496 \text{ m}^2$

Thus, length of collector

$L_c = 0.6890 \text{ m} = 2.260 \text{ feet}$ For safety design it is taken as 4 feet.

2. Collector efficiency: A measure of collector performance is the collector efficiency, defined as the ratio of useful heat gain over any time period to the incident solar radiation over the same period. Therefore

C. Construction

The solar food dryer was constructed as per the designed dimension by making use of locally available and relatively cheap materials. Since the entire casing was made of wood and the cover is glass, the major construction works is carpentry works.

The metal sheet used was mild steel of 1mm thickness. It was cut to the size of 1.2192×0.6096mm. It was painted black for maximum absorption of solar radiation. The metal sheet was placed inside the air heater (solar collector) compartment. The glass was cut into size of 1.2192 × 0.6096 mm² size and one of these were required as the solar collector cover. The glass used was clear glass with 4 mm thickness. The trays were made with wooden frames and wire mesh to permit free flow of air within the drying cabinet (chamber). Four trays were used with average of 6cm spacing arranged vertically one on top of the other, the tray size was 60 × 33cm. a steel stand was constructed for giving required tilt to solar collector.

D. Materials:

The tomatoes dried in this experiment were grown locally, was of medium size, and the colour was orange to red. They were bought on the local market the same morning the drying was to be performed. 1 kg of tomato was taken for this experiment.

Para meter consider

1. Initial moisture content of tomato= 94%
2. Moisture content of dry tomato=10%
3. Maximum allowable temperature=600c

Pre-treatment: Firstly wash the tomato with water and dry it with cloth. Now cut it into four equal parts and adopt the following procedure. Citric acid dip: Citric acid is mixed with water at 2% by weight. Tomato is placed in this solution for few second, drain and placed on trays.

At the time of starting the trial temperature, relative humidity and velocity of ambient air was measured with the help of thermometer, hygrometer and anemometer

that drying rate is high at the initially and goes on decreasing with time due to less and less moisture available for evaporation.

respectively. During trial time the various parameters of air at inlet and outlet of collector, in the drying chamber and at outlet of drying chamber was measured at hourly intervals the moisture content were determined.

E. Observation Table

Trial time: 10:40 am Date: 29/1/2014

Initial weight of tomato=1kg

Ambient condition:

1. Temperature= 24.20c.
2. Relative humidity= 13%
3. Air speed= 0.2 m/s
4. Volume flow rate of air= $0.37 \times 0.045 \times 0.2 = 3.33 \times 10^{-3} \text{m}^3/\text{s}$
5. Mass flow rate of air= $1.28 \times 3.33 \times 10^{-3} \text{kg/s}$

Table 1. Performance Factor

Time (hr)	% moisture	Drying rate(Mi- Mf)/t
0	94	(gm/hr)
3	74.14	70.66
6	55.16	67.33
9	35.93	68.33
12	25.83	35.67
15	15.42	37
18	10.46	17.67

IV. RESULT

In this work passive solar dryer is designed, constructed and its performance is evaluated for tomato and following result were obtained.

Graph 1.shows temp Vs time indicates that temp is increases from morning time reaches at peak at noon and again decreases after that.

Figure 1: Moisture content (%) Vs drying time (hr)

Graph 2 shows moisture content (%) vs. drying time indicates that moisture removal rate is initially high because of presence of unbound moisture which evaporates at higher rate and goes on decreasing with time.

Figure 2:-Drying rate Vs day time

Graph 3 shows drying rate verses drying time indicates

Figure 3: Collector Outlet temperature Vs day time.

CONCLUSION

In the construction we use wood as a primary material which leads to cost reduction and making it affordable to all. This will go a long way in reducing food wastage of most of the agro-commodity and at the same time food shortages. Apart from this, solar energy is required for its operation which is a clean form of energy. It protects the environment and saves cost.

REFERENCES

- [1]. F.K. Forson, M.A.A. Nazha, F.O. Akuffo, H. Rajakaruna, Design Of Mixed-Mode Natural Convection Solar Crop Dryers: Application Of Principles And Rules Of Thumb, Leicester Le1 9bh, Uk Received 9 August 2006; Accep Ted 15 December 2006, Available Online 22 February 2007.
- [2]. Shanmugam, E. Natarajan, Technical note Experimental investigation of forced convection and desiccant integrated solar dryer, Received 5 March 2005; accepted 31 May 2005; Available online 10 August 2005 3) M. Mohanraj, p. Chandrasekar, postharvest technology drying of copra in a forced convection solar drier.
- [3]. Oguntola j. Alamu, collins n. Nwaokocha, and olayinka adunola, design and construction of a domestic passive solar food dryer, leonardo journal of sciences, issn 1583- 0233.
- [4]. B.H. Khan ,”Non-Conventional Energy Resources Book, mcgraw hill publication.